

IMPACT OF SOCIAL CULTURAL FACTORS ON PURCHASE INTENTION OF COUNTERFEIT MOBILE PHONES

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Abstract: Counterfeit consumption has been on an upsurge globally aided by comparative higher trade margins and increasing demand for renowned brands at lower prices. Social cultural factors have been found to play a major role in the growth of the trade as they influence the intention hence purchase of such goods. Findings on what motivates this trade are not yet not conclusive, necessitating further study. The objective of this study therefore was to investigate the effect of social cultural factors on the purchase intention of counterfeit mobile phones. The study applied an explanatory research design among university students, with a target population of 500 drawn from young and middle generations within universities in Kenya.

A well-structured questionnaire with a 5 point Likert scale was used as the data collection tool and simple random methods used to collect the data. Cronbach's alpha was used to test for the instrument reliability. The study adopted positivism research paradigm to collect data from the target population. Excluding missing data and outliers from the 500 students sampled, data collected from 450 respondents were analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics analysis in the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to determine the relationship of social cultural factors and purchase intention with the significance of the relationship being tested at 95% confidence level ($P=0.05$). The results revealed that Social cultural factors have positive and significant effect ($\beta=0.579$, $r^2 = 0.332$, $P<0.05$) on consumer purchase intention towards counterfeit mobile phone among the young and middle aged generations in Kenya. This study will help government agencies to understand some new ways to combat the illicit trade as well as mobile phone marketers who will devise ways to fight against the unfair competition posed by fake products.

Keywords: purchase intention, social cultural factors, counterfeits.

1. INTRODUCTION

Understanding the factors contributing to the increased use of counterfeits products is key in establishing how to deal with counterfeits. Knowledge of the underlying factors that influences consumers' tendency to purchase counterfeit products is essential to determine the most appropriate anti-counterfeiting actions. This is so because consumption of counterfeit goods has been on the increase and has become a major concern in the world because of the disastrous effect it has on genuine business. Counterfeit consumption is a growing phenomenon, with studies estimating that 59% to 70% of the North American population has engaged in this behavior (Canadian Anti-Counterfeiting Network, 2007; Nia & Zaichkowsky, 2000; Walthers & Buff, 2008). In the past two decades, counterfeit branding has grown tremendously in an organized form, especially in luxury brand industries (Agha, 2015; Stöttinger & Penz, 2015).

The vice has been in the increase because of the expensive and high-status characteristics of some brands, increasing consumer information about leading brands and the desire of consumers to purchase and enjoy the best brands the world has to offer and the inefficiencies in the supply chain for genuine goods.

According to Bian and Veloutsou (2007), counterfeits are the goods which bear a logo that is identical to, or indistinguishable from, a trademark registered to another party, therefore infringing the rights of the holder of the trademark. Gillani, (2012) defines purchase intention as the act of dealing between customer and retailer to purchase something willingly. Purchase intention can predict the chances of a buyer making a purchase, the greater the purchase intention is, the larger the chance that a buyer will purchase given merchandise (Dodds et al. 1991; Schiffman and Kanuk, 2000). On the other hand Swami *et al.*, (2009) reported that social cultural factors and consumerism vary with cultural contexts and is situation specific. Social cultural factors define and affect the way one thinks and acts even in different situations including in the area of consumption. The existence of culture among human groups makes human being one of the most superlative beings created by nature (Harris, 1995; Ritzier, 2011). Technically, culture represents all of human behaviors and attitudes that are learned (directly or indirectly, overtly or covertly) through the process of social interaction and which are inherited by generations. Allen, Ng, & Wilson (2002) argued that consumers' values and ethics predict consumers' attitudes and behaviors because values motivate people to select actions or objects that fulfill their values. This includes purchase and consumption. Studies have illustrated that culture, especially as it differs across countries, has significant effects on both the demand and supply sides of counterfeiting (Eining and Christensen 1991; Nyaw and Ng 1994; Swinyard et al. 1990; Vitell, Nwachukwu, and Barnes 1993).

Since studies have shown that Counterfeit merchandise now cuts across various industries in business-to-consumer and business-to-business markets in developed and emerging economies alike, there is need to find ways to reduce the vice by looking at both demand and supply sides of the illegal business. There is contention that the supply side of counterfeiting has received considerable attention in the literature, but investigations focusing on the demand side are still scarce, hence the need for further studies in the area. (Ang, Cheng, Lim, and Tambyah 2001; Bloch, Bush and Campbell 1993; Dubinsky and Nataraajan, and Huang 2005) .

This study focuses on examining the effect of social cultural factors on consumer intention to purchase counterfeit mobile phones among Kenyan aged 20 to 50 with the aim of giving more insight of the perceived relationship between the two variables.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research design

The study adopted explanatory research design based on the causal-effect relationship (Hair et al, 2013) and employed cross sectional self-administered questionnaire as the main data collection instrument, to collect data at one point in time to explore the factors that inform consumer social cultural factors and attitudes towards counterfeits. According to Mark, Phillip & Adrian (2009), studies that seek to establish causal relationship between variables use explanatory design, since this design is premised on describing, analyzing and interpreting relationships among variables as well as hypothesis formulation and objectively testing relationships

2.2 Target population, sample and sampling technique

The study assessed the effect of social cultural factors on the purchase intention of mobile phone counterfeits focusing on individuals aged 20-50. Natal Jamal *et al.*, (2012) agrees that when asking individuals over the age of 50 about counterfeits and piracy, they are likely to be doubtful and may not have knowledge about the subject hence the reason why 20-50 age brackets was used in this study. The study concentrated on the Baby Boomers (born 1946 to 1965), Generation X (born 1965 to 1977) and Generation Y (born 1977 to 1998). The survey was conducted among the three generations of Kenyans in Nairobi County. University students in the three identified cohorts constitute an appropriate sample for this study because students are likely to be heavy users of product categories that are frequently counterfeited (Cordell et al., 1996) and researchers have identified college students as one consumer segment that knowingly purchases counterfeits (Chakraborty, Allred, Sukhdial, & Bristol, 1997). The method of sampling was random convenient sampling among members of the three cohorts. These cohorts were selected for this study because they represent the largest adult consumer groups at present, ranging in age from 18 to 69 years. A sample size 500 respondents spread across the three cohorts was used which elicited for representativeness, efficiency, flexibility and accuracy of data. Probability sampling was used as it's the most appropriate in quantitative research since respondents are selected randomly; giving researchers an heterogeneous sample more representative than a non-random sample and enabling generalization to the population as reported by Bryman & Bell (2012). The university population was considered to be fit for this study, given the type of the research. The majority of university students lie into age group of 18-50 years which is consistent with the target population.

2.3 Data collection instrument

A well-structured questionnaire was used for data collection and Cronbach's alpha was used to test the reliability of the measures of the instrument. Bryman (2011) suggests that where Cronbach Alpha is used for reliability test, a rule of thumb is also used that states that the Cronbach values of the items in the study should not be lower than 0.7. To increase the reliability of the questionnaire, this study used Cronbach's Alpha for separate domains of the questionnaire rather than the entire questionnaire. Pilot testing was done to assist in determining if there are flaws, limitations, or other weakness within the interview design. This provided the opportunity to revise and amended relevant issues and make changes where necessary before the survey instrument was distributed to the actual sample. The survey instrument was pre-tested with a group of 45 individuals who fall within the Criteria of the unit of analysis. The final questionnaire contained a total of 57 items which were measured on 5-point scales, with anchors ranging from 1 denoting a very negative view and 5 indicating a very positive view. The questionnaire consisted of both open-ended questions and some structured closed-ended questions on a customized five-part Likert scale to collect data on the independent variables from the respondents. Respondents were asked to indicate agreement with each item on a five-point scale Likert scale ranging from 1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=neutral, 4=agree, and 5=strongly agree. The scales used were tested for convergent validity using Cronbach alpha coefficients and those with coefficient above 0.7 were deemed to be acceptable.

2.4 Data Collection Methods and Sources

Data was collected using a Web-based survey sent to the three target cohorts randomly selected in the universities located in the selected districts of Nairobi using self-administered survey forms. Bryman and Bell (2011) reports that self-completion questionnaire ensures objectivity since the respondent answers without the aid of an interviewer. Survey method was used in this study as it is the most common method regarding social science when the predicted population is too large to be observed (Bryman & Bell, 2005).

According to Hair et. al. (2003) each variable should be measured by at least three items in order to be valid. As a measure of attitude, a Likert scale is designed to allow respondents to rate how strongly they agree or disagree with carefully constructed statements, ranging from very positive to very negative attitudes toward some object.

The table below (table 1) shows where measures of various variables are borrowed from.

Table 1: Measurements of Variables/Constructs and their sources

Variable/ Construct	Reference for Measure/ Sources	No of Items
Purchase intentions	Zeithaml et al 1996	5
SCF-Materialism	Marsha L Richins 1992	16
SCF-Moral Intensity	Angel et al 2001	4
SCF-Subjective norms	Shih I Cheng et al 2011, Azjen 1991	5
SCF-Value Consciousness	Lichtenstein&Burton1989; Peterson&Wilson 1985).	11

2.5 Data analysis and presentation

The data was analysed using both descriptive statistics and inferential statistics including correlation analysis, analysis of variance and regression using SPSS. Age, gender and marital status were treated as controlled variables giving unique effects of IV on DV. To get descriptive statistics, measures of central tendency like mean and standard deviation were used to assess data characteristics and show variation in frequency of items. Inferential statistics were used to test the hypothesized relationships so as to allow generalization of the findings to a larger population. To establish the relationships between the study variables, simple regression equations were used. According to Pall (2010), regression analyses provides estimate equations to predict the magnitude of the dependent variable and provide values for the predictor variables to get how much of the variance in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variables. Pearson Correlation analysis was done to show the nature and strength of the relationship among variables of the study. The relationship was considered strong when $r = 0.5$ and above, moderately strong when r is between 0.3 and 0.49, weak when r is below 0.29, and a correlation of 0 indicates no relationship. Coefficient of determination (r^2) was used to determine goodness of the prediction model and used to measure the amount or degree of variation in the dependent variable attributed to the predictor variable.

2.6 Statistical measurement model

A model serves an important duty in a study as it allows for specification of relationships between variables Hair *et al.*, (2010). The relationship between social cultural factors and consumer purchase intension was given by the following equation:

$$PI = \alpha + \beta X + e$$

Where:

PI = Intention to Purchase counterfeits

X = Social Cultural factors

α = constant and the model equation intercept

β = Beta value

e = Error term.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Sample Characteristics

Table 2 shows the sample characteristics of the study. Both gender (male and female), age sets, married and singles groups were represented in this study. Out of the 500 questionnaires administered, only 450 were returned representing 90% response rate. According to Mugenda (2003) a response rate of above 70% is acceptable in research.

Table 2: Sample characteristics

Characteristics	Category	Frequency	%
Gender	Female	242	54.2
	Male	205	45.6
Age	18-24	195	43.3
	25-34	127	28.2
	34-44	78	17.3
	>45	50	11.2
Marital Status	Single	243	54.0
	Married	207	46.0

3.2 Descriptive Statistics

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of Social cultural factors on the purchase intention of counterfeit mobile phones in Kenya. Descriptive statistics for the response on both purchase intention (DV) and social cultural factors (IV) was performed as detailed in sub-section 2.5.1 to 2.5.2.

3.3 Purchase Intentions

Table 3: Response on purchase intention

Opinions	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev.
Think about a counterfeited product as a choice when buying something	450	1	5	2.23	1.196
Buy a counterfeited product	450	1	5	2.15	1.173
Recommend to friends and relatives that they buy a counterfeit product	450	1	5	1.93	1.156
Recommend to friends and relatives that they buy a counterfeited phone	450	1	5	1.96	1.208
Say favourable things about counterfeit phones.	450	1	5	2.07	1.263

Key: 1=strongly disagree; 2= Disagree, 3= Agree 4= Neutral, 5=strongly agree

3.3.1 Social cultural factors

Social cultural factors were measured using 32 items in the four dimensions of materialism, subjective norms, value consciousness and moral intensity using four statements on a Likert scale. Results in table 4 below indicate that the respondents were impartial (neutral) on the aspects measuring social cultural factors with a mean range of 4.05 to 4.32. The results also show that the respondents had diverse views as the standard deviation for each component was greater than 1.

Table 4: Response on Social cultural factors

Mean and SD for Social Cultural Factors		
SUBJECTIVE NORMS	Mean	S. D
How important are peers/colleagues approval for your purchases	3.07	1.293
How important are important friends approval for your purchase	3.14	1.303
How important is your parents approval for your purchase of new items	3.17	1.388
How important are your siblings approval for your purchase of new items	3.16	1.340
My relatives and friends approve my decision to buy counterfeited products	2.14	1.308
MATERIALISM		
The important achievements in life include acquiring material possessions	3.42	1.312
I don't view the material objects people own as sign of success	3.04	1.285
The things I own say a lot about how well I'm doing in life	3.38	1.299
I like to own things that impress people.	2.85	1.341
I don't pay much attention to the material objects other people own	3.03	1.278
MATERIALISM-Centrality		
I usually buy only the things I need.	3.22	1.312
I try to keep my life simple, as far as possessions are concerned	3.32	1.278
The things I own aren't all that important to me.	2.54	1.288
I enjoy spending money on things that aren't practical.	2.16	1.280
Buying things gives me a lot of pleasure.	3.00	1.265
I like a lot of luxury in my life.	2.83	1.284
I put less emphasis on material things than most people I know	3.08	1.274
MATERIALISM-Happiness		
I have all the things I really need to enjoy life.	2.39	1.226
My life would be better if I owned certain things I don't have	3.51	1.301
I'd be happier if I could afford to buy more things.	3.59	1.284
It bothers me quite a bit that i can't afford all the things I would like	3.49	1.289

Key: 1=strongly disagree; 2= Disagree, 3=Agree 4=Neutral 5=strongly agree

3.4 Reliability Analysis

Reliability analysis was performed on both dependent and independent variables to ascertain the properties of measurement scale and the items that compose the scales. The range of the Cronbach Alpha obtained was within the acceptable levels as elaborated in the table 5 below. This indicated a strong internal consistency among measures of variable items. Nachmias and Nachmias (2006) explained that a Cronbach's alpha test confirms the reliability and consistency of a tool. According to Sekaran (2010), the closer the alpha is to 1 the higher the reliability and a value of at least 0.7 is recommended. An alpha coefficient higher than 0.70 signifies that the gathered data has a relatively high internal consistency and could be generalized to reflect the respondent's opinions on the study problem.

Table 5: Reliability Analysis

Variable	No. of items	Cronbach's Alpha	Standardized Cronbach's Alpha
Social Cultural Factors(SCF)	32	0.832	0.835
Purchase Intention (PI)	5	0.865	0.865

3.5 Factor Analysis

According to Bartholomew *et al.*, (2011), factor analysis operates on the notion that measurable and observable variables can be reduced to fewer latent variables that share a common variance and are unobservable, which is known as reducing dimensionality. To achieve this, both the dependent variable (purchase intention) and independent variable (social cultural factors) were subjected to factor reduction as detailed in subsections 2.7.1 to 2.7.2.

3.5.1 Factor Analysis on Purchase Intention

Table 9 shows that the variance explained for the dependent variable purchase intention (PI). Before carrying out factor analysis on the Purchase Intention, the data was checked for adequacy for Factor analyses through KMO test. The KMO test (Table 6) showed that the data was adequate for Factor analysis since the KMO score was 0.801 while the Bartlett's Test of Sphericity showed significance with a Chi Square (χ^2) of 1202.4 at $P < 0.01$. This indicated that the data was good for factor analysis as the factors were not an identity matrix.

TABLE 6: (KMO TEST and Bartlett's test for Purchase Intention)

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.801
	Approx. Chi-Square (χ^2)	1202.384
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Df	10
	Sig.	.000

The five (5) factors that were considered to explain purchase intention underwent component analysis with varimax rotation and only one component was extracted. This component had Eigen value than 1(3.276) and explained 65.5% of the variance observed in purchase intention which means 65.5 per cent of the common variance shared by the five factors could be explained by that component with original factors loading into this component in various degrees. The factor with the highest contribution to the component (Recommend to friends and relatives that they buy a counterfeited phone=0.889) was chosen to be the name of the component extracted. That factor was therefore used to mean purchase intention in the subsequent analysis.

TABLE 7: COMPONENT ANALYSES

Questionnaire item	Factor loading
Think about a counterfeited product as a choice when buying something	.655
Buy a counterfeited product	.758
Recommend to friends and relatives that they buy a counterfeit product	.880
Recommend to friends and relatives that they buy a counterfeited phone	.889
Say favorable things about counterfeit phones	.841

Table 8: Total Variance Explained on Purchase Intention

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.276	65.520	65.520	3.276	65.520	65.520
2	.838	16.762	82.281			
3	.420	8.403	90.685			
4	.300	6.008	96.693			
5	.165	3.307	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

3.6 Factor Analysis on Social cultural factors

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) was run for Social Cultural Factors to determine if the factors there in were adequate to be run through factor analysis. The KMO results gave a measure of 0.806, which was above the threshold of 0.6 (Field, 2006). The Bartlett's test was also significant in this study with chi square $\chi^2 = 4437.262$ (p-value, 0.000). Therefore, the KMO value of 0.806 and significance of Bartlett's statistic confirmed the appropriateness of the factor analysis for the data set. Consequently the thirty two measures of Social Cultural Factors were subjected to factor analysis and the results (Table 9) showed that there were eight critical factors driving SCF, which accounted for 61.4% of the total variance. The other factors loaded into these 8 factors and consequently the 8 would be picked to adequately explain social cultural factors as shown below.

TABLE 9: FACTOR ANALYSES

Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	6.005	18.766	18.766	3.748	11.714	11.714
2	3.859	12.060	30.826	3.398	10.617	22.331
3	2.183	6.821	37.647	2.979	9.311	31.642
4	2.088	6.524	44.171	2.360	7.376	39.018
5	1.721	5.379	49.550	2.324	7.263	46.281
6	1.366	4.270	53.820	1.808	5.649	51.930
7	1.269	3.967	57.787	1.541	4.815	56.745
8	1.158	3.618	61.405	1.491	4.660	61.405
9	.986	3.081	64.486			
10	.960	3.000	67.486			
11	.904	2.826	70.312			
12	.826	2.580	72.891			
13	.779	2.433	75.325			
14	.733	2.289	77.614			
15	.719	2.248	79.862			
16	.640	2.001	81.863			
17	.638	1.994	83.857			
18	.539	1.686	85.543			
19	.508	1.588	87.131			
20	.480	1.500	88.631			
21	.434	1.355	89.986			
22	.409	1.279	91.264			
23	.395	1.235	92.500			
24	.374	1.170	93.670			
25	.359	1.121	94.790			
26	.333	1.042	95.832			
27	.313	.978	96.810			
28	.275	.860	97.669			
29	.244	.762	98.431			
30	.188	.587	99.018			
31	.164	.512	99.531			
32	.150	.469	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

3.6.1 Normality Test

To facilitate further analysis, the study determined if data followed a normal distribution and followed a bell shaped curve. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2011) the assumption of normality is important for fitting linear regression model. If data distribution has normality; it is possible to do inferential and parametric statistical analysis with minimal chance of outliers. In this study, normality of data was checked to ensure that any errors in prediction of value the dependent variable are distributed in a way that approaches the normal (Ghasemi&Zahediasal, 2012). Table 10 presents

the normality test results in which considering the skewness and kurtosis statistics the data was assumed to be normal. According to George & Mallery (2010), values for asymmetry and kurtosis between -2 and +2 are considered acceptable in order to prove normal univariate distribution. The data for Purchase Intention could therefore be taken for further test of linearity.

Table 10: Normality test

	Purchase Intention	SCF
N Valid	450	450
Skewness	1.137	1.236
Std. Error of Skewness	.115	.115
Kurtosis	.201	.652
Std. Error of Kurtosis	.230	.230

3.6.2 Correlation Analysis

Pearson’s Correlation analysis was used to establish the relationship between social cultural factors and purchase intention. The analysis measures of linear association between two variables and was used to identify the strength and direction of the associations among the variables of the study.

Table 11 shows that the independent variable Social cultural factor correlated strongly with Purchase Intention ($r = 0.579$, $p < 0.01$)

According to Hair et al., (2006) correlation coefficient (r) ranging from .81 and 1.0 are very strong; from .61 to .80 are strong; from .41 to .60 moderate; from .21 to .40 weak; and from .00 and .20 indicates no relationship, hence the correlation between SCF and purchase intention was deemed Strong.

Table 11: Correlations of the study variables

		PI	SCF
PI	Pearson Correlation	1	
SCF	Pearson Correlation	.579**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$ (2-tailed). N = 450.

Source: Survey data (2015)

3.7 Regression Analysis

The study hypothesized that social cultural factors had no influence on the purchase intention of counterfeit mobile phones in Kenya. The results in table 12 below show that Social cultural factors were found to have positive and significant effect on purchase intention of counterfeits ($\beta=0.579$, $P<0.05$). The standardized Beta value of 0.579 implies that with every unit increase in Social Cultural factors, Purchase intention of counterfeits increases by 0.579 units indicating that SCF explains up to 58% of the variation in Purchase intention of counterfeits.

Table 12: for Regression Analyses for Social Cultural Factors and Purchase Intention

Coefficients		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
Model	(Constant)	1.114	.149		7.492	.000
	SCF	.669	.044	.579	15.048	.000

- a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention (PI),
- b. Predictors: constant, Social Cultural Factors (SCF)

Model summary

A model summary run to check how well the model fits in explaining the predictive model led to the observation that the hypothesized model fits very well in the analysis hence it can be used to predict the model since the adjusted r^2 is 0.334.

An Anova test was done to check if the above relationship was significant. The anova table below (TABLE 13) indicates that the model was found to be significant $F(1,448) = 226.5, P < 0.05$ as a predictor of the equation ($p < 0.00$), which confirms that the predictor, Social Cultural Factors fits in the model very well and is therefore good in predicting the Dependent Variable, Purchase Intention.

Table 13: Model summary

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.579a	.336	.334	.32743

a. Predictors: (Constant), SCF

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	24.278	1	24.278	226.448	.000 ^b
	Residual	48.031	448	.107		
	Total	72.308	449			

a. Dependent Variable: PI

b. Predictors: (Constant), SCF

4. CONCLUSION

The results gave enough evidence, based on R^2 to justify the rejection of the null hypothesis as depicted by the regression and correlation analysis results below, and make the subsequent conclusion.

TABLE 14: HYPOTHESIS TEST

Hypothesis	Standardized beta value	Hypothesis test	Remark/ Decision
H_0 : Social cultural factors have no significant effect on the purchase intention of counterfeit mobile phones in Kenya.	Beta=0.579 $R^2=0.334$ P =0.000	Reject H_0 if $p \leq 0.05$ Fail to reject H_0 if $p > 0.05$	H_0 rejected at 95% CI

Researcher: 2015

Based on the results of the study Social cultural factors were found to have positive and significant effect in influencing customer purchase decision of mobile phone; therefore the study concluded that Social cultural factors have influence on customer purchase decision of counterfeit mobile phones. Based on this conclusion, mobile phone dealers specifically marketing managers need to find ways of incorporating social cultural factor variables like materialism and value consciousness in their marketing differentiation strategies

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

It is recommended that social cultural factors should be considered among other factors as key in fighting mobile phone counterfeiting. To managers and brand builders the results offer several suggestions to help in navigating the markets in current economic conditions and market realities. It offers knowledge and advice on the areas to target in messaging and branding. For instance it shows the need to be innovative in luxury goods and to scale down the versions of goods available in various markets since the study showed that non deceptive counterfeits are bought by buyers who just want to make do with some fairly good product. This would encourage some to buy cheaper counterfeits if they cannot afford the original item. Innovation and production of lower versions of the new products would give such consumers options so that they don't result to counterfeits. Innovation would also make production of the new product cheaper especially if targeted for mass market and this ensure it is still within the reach of the majority. Mobile phone dealers specifically marketing managers need to find ways of incorporating social cultural factor variables like materialism and value consciousness in their marketing differentiation strategies.

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